

Impact of Capacity Building on The Performance of Teaching Staff in Federal University Birnin Kebbi

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of Capacity Building on the Performance of teaching staff in Federal University Birnin-Kebbi (FUBK). The study adopts survey research design. The population of the study consists of 495 teaching staff of Federal University, Birnin- Kebbi. Krejcie and Morgan Table (1970) was used to arrive at sample of 214 respondents which were selected using simple random sampling technique. The data generated was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics using SPSS version 26, while Human Capital Development theory was used as the theoretical framework that underpinned the study. The finding shows that mentoring, training and development has a positive and significant impact on the performance of teaching staff in Federal University, Birnin Kebbi. The research recommends that, the University management should give more emphasis to mentoring; training and development to enhance the performance of their teaching staff in order to enable them to achieve their mission and vision.

Keywords: Capacity Building, Performance, Training and Development and Mentoring.

Introduction

The success or failure of every organization whether public or private, product or service-oriented organization largely depends on the performance of its employees. Employee's performance is central to the attainment of organizational goals and objectives. Several empirical evidences shown that, there is nexus between employee's performance and attainment of organisational goals and objectives. For example, Samuel (2018) studied the effect of employee performance on organizational performance in Tanzania in which the finding indicates a significant and positive relationship between employee performance and attainment of organisational objectives. Hence, most organizations nowadays understand that, the performance of their workers plays an important role to their success, expansion and accomplishment of their objectives. As such organizations most, developed different strategies, techniques, methods and procedure in order to enhance the performance of their workers so as to enable them achieve their stated goals and objectives.

Studies such as (Ahmed et al. 2015, Erastus & Maiyo, 2013) have shown that, among the technique and procedure used by many organizations around the world to boost the performance of their workers is capacity building. As such, organizations around the world are heavily investing in capacity building in order to improve the performance of their employee. For example, University of Chicago in the United State has established and maintained Professional Development Funds through which monies are made available for training and development of teaching staff in the university where each full-time faculty member received a minimum of 2,500 dollars for professional development annually. In Nigeria, the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TET FUND) is said to have invested over 190 billion from 2008 to 2023 for training of teaching staff in Nigeria's public tertiary institutions (Vanguard, 2024).

Capacity Building is seen as the process of strengthening and developing skills, abilities, resources and procedure that an organization needs to survive and remain competitive in a dynamic world. Thus, it is seen as the development of employee's knowledge, professional skills, leadership capacity for decision making and performance so as to ensure

organizational development and effective performance. Hence, it can be described as a process, technique or method through which an organization build and enhance the skills, knowledge, abilities and competence of its workers to effectively and efficiently perform their functions in order to achieve organizational goals and objectives. e. Capacity Building can improve workers performance which will invariably lead to the increase in overall organizational performance, reduce cost, enhance quality and minimize conflict in an organization. The findings of most previous studies shown that there is a positive and significant relationship between capacity building and workers performance (Ahmad et al., 2015).

University is an institution of tertiary education and academic research which award academic degrees in several disciplines. Globally, universities are established to play an important role in teaching, learning, research and technological development. They provide professional training for high level jobs as well as education necessary for the development of personality and nation. Ibor (2021) opined that, Universities plays an important role in providing development researches and recommendation for policy making and implementation in order to solve existential problems; creating technological products and producing new knowledge that can be adapted for economic, political and social development.

Solomon et al., (2020) documented that in Nigeria, universities are established in order to contribute to the development of intellectual capacities of individual to understand and appreciate their environment and become a useful member of the society. Universities are expected to contribute to economic growth and development through teaching, research, publications and service to communities (Ibor, 2021). For Nigerian universities to undertake these important tasks or functions and positively contribute to the economic growth and development they must possess and maintained a well-trained, experienced and qualified teaching staff.

However, failure to invest in capacity building may lead to low performance of employees which may result to poor organizational performance. Similarly, Gabedi (2004) submitted that, inadequate funding is among the major constraints undermining the operations of public universities in Nigeria. Due to poor funding public universities in Nigeria become financially in capable to sponsor their teaching staff for training and development. Also, empirical evidences have shown that, failure to provide opportunity for mentoring; training and development have negatively affected the performance of teaching staff in Nigeria's public tertiary institutions which seriously undermine the quality of teaching, quality of research and publications and students' performance (Gabedi, 2004). To remedy this problem, Tertiary Education Trust Funds was established by the federal government of Nigeria and assigned with task of staff training and development in the public tertiary institutions. Over the years, TET Fund was said to have expanded huge and substantial amount of money for training and development of teaching staff in Nigeria's public tertiary institutions both within and outside the country. The research work is therefore and attempts to assess the impact of capacity building on the performance of teaching staff in Federal University, Birnin Kebbi.

Conceptual Review

Concept of Capacity Building

The concept of Capacity Building was first used by the United Nation in 1950 to refer to enhancing technological and self-help capacities for individual's rural areas (Makau, 2017). In 1970s United Nation Development Programme (UNDP) used the term Capacity Building to refer to enhancing capacity of technical skills for administrative sectors of developing countries. Also in 1980s the concept Capacity Building was used by International Development Agencies to imply a process necessary for strengthening and building developing countries government and equipping their both public and private agencies for economic and human capital development (Erastus & Maiyo, 2013).

Bergeron et al., (2017) opined that Capacity Building is beyond just training of workers in an organization to acquire new skills and knowledge but rather a holistic approach to personal development and effective performance of his work in an organization. In the sane vain Ahmad et al (2015) opined that Capacity Building is more than just access to information or new knowledge but an empowerment of individual to utilize the skills and knowledge for better performance. Also, Mango (2022) perceived Capacity Building as the process of strengthening and developing skills, abilities, resources and procedure that an organization needs to survive and remain competitive in a dynamic world.

Makau (2017) opined that, the term Capacity Building is sometime used interchangeably with manpower development but Capacity Building is more related to increasing the skills, knowledge and competence of workers to effectively carryout their functions in an organization and it is usually through mentoring, coaching, training and development. From these scholarly views trying to describe the concept Capacity Building one can deduce that, it is method, technique and process through which organization build and enhance the ability, competence, skill and knowledge of its workers to effectively perform their functions in order to achieve its goals and objectives. It is important to state that, capacity building can take place at three different levels which are institutional or organizational level, societal level and individual level. However, Erastus and Maiyo (2013) expressed that, capacity building recently focuses on individual

level that mainly concern with improving the competence, skills and knowledge of individual workers to effectively carryout their tasks or functions in an organization.

Mentoring

Mentoring is perceived as assisting organization to increase the knowledge, skills and competence of it workers for a higher performance by attaching a less experienced workers with a relatively more experienced worker (Abomeh, 2015). Ramesh (2015) argues that mentoring is unlocking a person's potential to maximize his performance and helps him to learn. It can be describe as a relationship between a less experienced worker called mentee and more experienced worker called mentor. Abomeh (2015) opined that mentor is an experienced person that facilitates personal and professional growth of individual by sharing the knowledge and insight that have been learned through the years. Mentoring is therefore seen as a technique of building the capacity of workers in which more experienced worker helps the less experienced worker to acquire skills, knowledge, experience and competence of a given job.

In the same vein, Abomeh (2015) viewed mentoring a s a process by which person of superior rank and prestige instruct, counsel, guide and facilitate the intellectual and or career development of persons identify as protégées. Also, Ramesh (2015) documented that, mentoring is a close developmental relationship between two people in which a partner willingly avail himself of the full range of superior experience, knowledge, skill or status of the other partner in all sphere of human activities. Mentoring is also said to involve exchange of wisdom, learning and development of skills and knowledge about organization for the protégé's career progression (Akinbobola, 2013). It is important to state here that; there are two dimension of mentoring which are career support and psychological support function.

Training

The term training and development are sometimes confused and often used interchangeably when in fact the two concepts are technically different (Erastus & Maiyo, 2013). Makau (2017) observed that training is the learning activities directed toward acquisition of specific knowledge, skills and competence for the purpose of accomplishing a particular task or function. This clearly pointed out that training is essentially concerned with acquisition of knowledge, skill and competence so as to increase employee performance in carrying a particular job.

Olaniyan (2008) expressed that training, is a systematic and planned function to modify employees' behaviour through learning activities, programmes and events that helps to increase abilities, knowledge, skills and competence in order to perform a particular job effectively and efficiently. Also Imran (2013) documented that, training is teaching workers on how to perform their current job and helping them to acquire knowledge, skills and competence in order to effectively perform their current job. Abdullahi et al., (2018) stressed that, training is fundamentally important to human capital development and employee performance in an organization. Ganesh (2015) on the other hand in an attempt to describe the importance of training in improving workers performance maintained that, it is vehicle that takes organization to its destination within a stipulated time frame. Therefore, for any organization to survive the competitive world today must invest heavily on staff training.

Development

According to Ganesh and Indradevi (2015), development is described as a process whereby employee in an organization possess the knowledge, skill and competence required to perform their job effectively, take on new responsibilities and adapt to changing condition. Theresa (2012) in an attempt to differentiate between training and development provided that, development mainly focuses on building the knowledge, skill and competence of employee in an organization so that they will be prepared to take on new responsibilities and challenges. Erastus perceived development as any learning activity geared toward future needs rather than present needs and which is more concerned with career progression or growth than immediate performance. From this, it can be understood that development is the process by which employee acquired skills and competence needed not only for the present job but also for future task of increasing difficulty and scope. It is mostly used in relation to process of helping employees to improve their managerial, administrative and decision-making ability and competence.

Employee Performance

The term employee performance is sometime used to refer to job performance which suggest work performance achieve by an individual worker in an organization. It implies the work quantity and quality accomplished by an employee in the discharge of his functions in line with the assigned responsibilities. Erastus and Maiyo, (2013) reported that, employee performance is the result or level of success of an individual employee at a particular time in carrying out a particular function. Ahmad et al., (2015) refer employee performance as an employee's accomplishment of assigned tasks. They posited further that pre-determined standards are set against which actual performances are measured and that without any rule of measurement it will be difficult to assess performance.

It is pertinent to stated here that, organizations around the world have developed and used different criteria in order to periodically review and measure the performance of their employee. However, universities across the world have

developed different parameters which they used periodically to evaluate the performance of their teaching staff for the purpose of taken so many decisions about their employment such promotion, compensation, retention among other important decision(Gabedi, 2004). Similarly, it is important to mention here that, numerous criteria for measuring the performance of teaching staff is use by different universities in different part of the world and these performance measurement or criteria have been brought out by different studies such as (Mc Nay, 1997; Wills, Taylor, 1999; Mergen et al, 2000; Ashe- Eric, 2001; Mulford et al, 2004; Griffith, 2004). Also, Gabedi (2004) argued extensively that, these performance measurement criteria for teaching staff in universities can be classified into three types, namely universal dimensions, job content dimensions and other performance dimensions.

For instance, Molefe (2010) has adapted Universal dimension which has five key performance indicators (subject knowledge, assessment procedure, student- teacher relationship, organizational skills, and communication skills) in his study, Performance Measurement Dimension for Lecturers at Selected Universities: An International Perspective. For this current study however, three performance measurements which are quality of teaching, quality of research and Publication and student performance is adapted from the work igbojekwe and Chigozie (2015) and will be used to determine how Capacity Building (Mentoring, Training and Development) affect the performance of teaching staff in Federal University, Birnin Kebbi.

Theoretical Framework

This study employed Human Capital Development theory propounded by Schultz (1961) which suggests that employee's performance in an organization is as a result of a combination of factors ranging from knowledge, experience, skills, and expertise from the internal and external environments of an organization. Similarly, Mango (2022) viewed human capital as a knowledge, competency, attitude and behaviour embedded in an individual; while, Abdullahi et al., (2018) documented that, human capital is a combination of factors such as education, experience, training, intelligence, energy, work habits, trustworthiness, and initiative that affect the employee performance. Similarly, Mango (2022) reported that, training relating to the work performs by the employees helps in improving their performance and achievement of organizational goals.

Empirical Review

Erastus and Maiyo (2013) studied Capacity Building and Employee Performance in MTN communication limited Accra, Ghana. The study used structured questionnaire to generate primary data from the chosen respondents. Cross Tabulation and Pearson' chi square was used for data analysis and the finding shows that Capacity Building has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. In contrast to their study that used employee of private sector organization to examine the impact of capacity building on employee performance the current study used the employee of public university.

Ramesh, (2015) examined the effect of coaching and mentoring on employee performance in the United Kingdom Hotel Industry, in which the study used cross- sectional and quantitative approach to investigate how coaching and mentoring improve the workers performance in hotel industry in United Kingdom. A sample of 172 respondents were chosen among managers and supervisors of different hotels in the United Kingdom through convenience sampling technique, structured questionnaire was used in eliciting response from the chosen respondents and data collected was analysed by using regression with the help of SPSS version 20 and the research findings indicated that Coaching and Mentoring has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Contrary to this study that used convenience sampling technique in selecting the respondents for the survey who were the managers and supervisors of hotels in United Kingdom, the current study used simple random sampling technique in selecting the respondents for this study who are teaching staff in Federal University, Birnin Kebbi.

Also, Ahmad et al., (2015) investigated the effect of capacity building on Employee Performance in which questionnaire was used to collect the primary data from the chosen respondents among the staff of banking industry; regression was used for data analysis with the help of SPSS Version 20 and the result shows that Capacity Building enhances workers performance. Unlike their study that used banking industry to assess the effect of capacity building on employee performance the current study used Public University.

In the same vein, Makau, (2017) investigated the effect of Performance Management and Capacity Building on Employee Performance in Madison Insurance Company Limited, Kenya. The study used questionnaire to elicit response from the 154 respondents randomly selected among the 540 employees of the Insurance Company, regression was used in analyzing the primary data with the help of SPSS and the finding revealed that, there is significant and positive relationship between Performance Management, Capacity Building and Employee Performance.

Wassem (2019) examined the impact of capacity building and managerial support on employee's performance in which questionnaire was administered on the staff of textile industry in Pakistan in order to generate primary data. SPSS 23 and SmartPLS-3 software were used for analysis. The results indicated that, capacity building has a positive significant

impact on employee performance. Again, Chukwurah, Uzor, Iwuno and Chukwueloka (2020) studied capacity building and employee productivity in the Nigeria’s Public Sector in which survey design was adopted to guide the investigation, questionnaire was used to elicit responses from the respondents and chi-square was use for testing the hypotheses. The research findings show that, Capacity Building has positive and significant effect on workers performance.

Conceptual Framework

From the diagram above, it is shown that Capacity Building which comprises of mentoring, training and development is the independent variable while employee performance is dependent variable. The study is trying to establish a link between independent and dependent variable.

Methodology

This paper employed quantitative research design which describes a phenomenon by making use of numerical data that can be analysed through statistical technique. Survey Research is more appropriate and suitable for this study since the primary data used in this study was generated through the use of questionnaire and analysed using statistical tools which gives room for generalization on the research finding by using statistical technique. Additionally, similar studies conducted by some other researchers also adopted survey research design method for instance (Eratus & Maiyo, 2013) and (Makau 2017).

The population of this study comprises of 495 teaching staff of the Federal University Birnin Kebbi across six faculties and two academic units. Federal University Birnin Kebbi is chosen for this survey because of the easy accessibility to data and information which make this study successful. Simple random sampling technique was used in selecting the respondents, while Krejcie and Morgan table (1970) was used to determine the sample size for the study. Thus, the table recommended the selection of 214 respondents since the total target population is 495. However, in order to elicit responses from the respondents a structured questionnaire on 5- point Likert scale ranges from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree was used. And finally, the data generated for the study will be analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics using SPSS version 26.

Result and Findings

Responses Rates

Table 1: Responses Rate

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Properly Filled Returned	151	70.5%
Un Properly Filled and Returned	19	8.9%
Un Returned	44	20%
Total	214	100%

Source: Survey 2025

The table 1 above indicates that, a total of 214 questionnaires were distributed to the teaching staff of Federal University Birnin Kebbi ware randomly chosen from six faculties and two academic units. Similarly, 170 questionnaires were filled and returned while 44 questionnaires representing 20% were not returned. Also 19 questionnaires representing 8.9% were removed as 9 were not properly filled and 10 were outliers. Therefore, 151 questionnaires that were properly filled was analysed and this represents an overall successful rate of 70. 56% which is quite adequate, Mugenda (2003) and also Kothari (2004) opined that a response rate of above 50% is adequate for a descriptive study.

Table 2
Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square
1	.662 ^a	.438	.427

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Development, Mentoring, Training
b. Dependent Variable: Performance

The table above indicated that mentoring, training and development has 42.7% impact on workers performance and apart from these three variable there are other factors that has 57.3% effect on workers performance.

Table 3
Coefficients^a

Model	B	t	Sig.
(Constant)	.629	1.850	.066
Mentoring	.161	2.657	.009
Training	.269	3.330	.001
Development	.405	5.989	.000

- a. Dependent Variable: Performance

HYPOTHESES TESTING AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Hypothesis one stated that, Staff mentoring has no significant impact on the performance of teaching staff in Federal University Birnin Kebbi. The result of the analysis in the table above indicates a positive and significant impact at 5% level of significance. Based on the result shown in the table above the null hypothesis stated is rejected, and accept that staff mentoring has positive and significant impact on employee's performance. This also, is in line with the findings of the studies conducted by Ramesh (2015) who investigates the effect of Coaching and Mentoring on Employee Performance in the United Kingdom and Abomeh who studied the effect of mentoring on employee performance in selected family business in Abuja, Nigeria.

Hypothesis two of the study postulated that, staff training has no significant impact on performance of teaching staff in Federal University Birnin Kebbi. The result of the analysis revealed that, training has positive and significant impact at 1% level of significance on the performance of teaching staff in Federal University Birnin Kebbi, as such the null hypothesis stated is rejected and this is in agreement with the studies of Wachiuri and Makokha (2024) who investigated the influence of Training and Development on Employee Performance in County Government of Kiambu in which their findings show training has a positive and significant impact on employees performance. Also, Abdullahi et al., (2018) investigated the effect of Training and Development on the Performance of teaching staff in Kano State polytechnic in which their finding show that, training and development has positive and significant impact on the performance of teaching staff in Kano State University.

Hypothesis three of this study stated that, development has no positive and significant impact on the performance of teaching staff in Federal University Birnin Kebbi. However, the result of the analysis shows that development has positive and significant impact on the performance of teaching staff at Federal University Birnin Kebbi at 1% level of significance as such the null hypothesis is therefore rejected and accepted that, development has positive and significant impact on the Performance of teaching staff in Federal University Birnin Kebbi. This is also supported by the study of Ganesh (2015) who investigated the effect of training and development on employee performance in which his finding show a positive and significant impact of independent variable on dependent variable.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the impact of capacity Building on the Performance of teaching staff in Federal University, Birnini Kebbi. From the findings of the research, it is evidential that the proxies of capacity building adopted in the study which are Mentoring, Training and Development has a positive and significant impact on the Performance of teaching staff in Federal University, Birnin Kebbi. The study therefore concludes that, Capacity Building has a positive and significant impact on workers performance; as such universities need to heavily invest in capacity building to improve the performance of the employee so as to enable them to achieve their goals and objectives. The paper further recommends the need for universities to engage in training needs assessment before embarking on selecting workers for training and development. There is also the need to sensitize the senior colleague to engage in mentoring of junior staff.

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